

Annual Report

2019

SND

Swedish National Data Service

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Preface

The somewhat unique construction of SND, where operations are governed by higher education institutions, but largely financed by national infrastructure funds from the Swedish Research Council, has been further strengthened in 2019. As a consortium, SND has been able to welcome KTH Royal Institute of Technology and Chalmers University of Technology as new consortium members, which means that we are now governed by nine of the ten largest education institutions in Sweden*. Furthermore, the SND network has been expanded with Kristianstad University, University College Stockholm/Enskilda Högskolan Stockholm (EHS), and RISE Research Institutes of Sweden. That brings the network to a total of 32 research institutions and authorities at the end of 2019. The network's strong foundation among Swedish universities and research authorities is of utmost importance to be able to fulfil the Open Data needs of the research community, and we are now very well equipped for 2020; a year when SND also celebrates its 40th anniversary.

At the heart of all of SND's collaborations is the shared knowledge about research data and a vision to provide access to well-structured and well-documented research data to researchers. The SND staff, as well as many of

the employees associated with the activities in the member organisations, have taken part as both teachers and participants in a number of courses during the year. I want to particularly highlight that research data training for doctoral students is now provided at a number of universities, and that the research data course at the University of Borås has been organized twice in 2019.

Finally, we can also mention that thanks to the strong support of a number of large research data producers, SND has been appointed a national node in the Research Data Alliance (RDA), which is a central and important position for our work, both nationally and internationally. We are proud of this confidence, and as a node we will strive to make the accumulated knowledge within RDA benefit the research communities in Sweden, and to make RDA better known to individual researchers.

*Max Petzold,
Director of SND*

* Other members of the SND Consortium are: University of Gothenburg, Karolinska Institutet, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University.

Network and Consortium Events

At the end of 2019, the SND Network consisted of 32 members; 30 Swedish universities and two research oriented authorities, as listed on page 8. The network members are in different stages of establishing a local unit or function for managing research data, a Data Access Unit (DAU).

Network Meetings

During 2019, SND organised four network meetings, each with a different theme. The meetings gathered participants from most of the network members, as well as from other interested parties.

12 March, Data Management Plans – How and Why?

We saw a record number of participants (117) in the first network meeting of the year in Gothenburg, which had the theme “Data management plans – how and why?” The topic was discussed from a variety of angles and several actors presented their view.

The opening speaker was Sanja Halling from the Swedish Research Council (VR), who gave a brief presentation of the council’s coordinating mission regarding open

access to research data, and introduced the VR workgroup for a national DMP tool. Several other representatives from this workgroup also attended the network meeting. Among them, the SUHF (the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions) research data group, represented by Sabina Anderberg. She outlined the recommendations that the SUHF research data group, together with VR and SND, are working on. The recommendations will serve as a foundation for the continued efforts with data management plans. Sofia Särdaqvist from the Swedish National Archives (RA) emphasised the importance of coordinating the DMP work with the archival descriptions. The information that has to be described according to the National Archive's general regulations (RA-FS) could also be included in a data management plan.

The technical aspects of a DMP tool were discussed by representatives from SNIC and SND, who are also members of the VR workgroup. Dejan Vitlacil from SNIC argued that the increasing need for storage of research data creates a demand for more guidelines and policies on how the e-infrastructures should manage data. Johan Fihn Marberg and Olof Olsson from SND contributed with a presentation of the existing DMP tools and pointed out their strengths and weaknesses. They also posed important questions about a possible multilingual integration of university-specific systems, export formats, and how a DMP template could be structured in order to be understood by humans as well as machines.

In Norway, the experiences from using DMPs are greater than in Sweden. Margrete Fotland and Joakim Dyrnes from the University of Oslo talked about their current work in creating a DMP template. A template that is already being used in Norway has been developed by the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD), and was demonstrated by Trond Kvamme.

Karin Meyer Lundén and Malin Almstedt Jansson presented the results of a researcher questionnaire from the University of Gävle in SND's network meeting in June.

3–4 June, Our Work with Researchers

This network meeting was hosted by University of Gävle and lasted for two half days. On the first day, Malin Almstedt Jansson and Karin Meyer Lundén, librarians and hosts for the network meeting, presented the results of a questionnaire that had been sent to researchers at University of Gävle to get an overview of the researchers' routines for data management and attitudes to sharing and re-using data. Later on, Sanja Halling from the Swedish Research Council gave an update on recent developments in the work with a national tool for data management plans. Stefan Ekman and Gustav Nilsson, SND Domain Specialists in the Humanities and Medicine, respectively, outlined the role of the domain specialist and gave a brief presentation of the development in their research domains.

Day two contained parallel sessions. The alternatives were *"The research data pilot – experiences and discussion"*, *"How do we know what researchers (don't) know about data management?"*, *"Exploring the resources in the DAU Handbook"*, and *"What to address in future training*

workshops?". This was the first network meeting with parallel sessions, and the experience was all over positive.

3 October, The F and R in FAIR

This network meeting in Gothenburg focused on the F and R in FAIR, meaning the efforts in making data Findable and Reusable. The topic was discussed in a panel session as well as in smaller groups. Before the discussions, the participants listened to a presentation by the keynote speaker: academic librarian Leif Longva from UiT The Arctic University of Norway. Norway has generally progressed further than Sweden in their work with open research data, and Leif Longva had been invited to present his experiences from developing and managing the research data function at the University of Tromsø.

The rest of the day was dedicated to discussions about the FAIR theme from various viewpoints. SND's Ulf Jakobsson gave an introduction to FAIR with focus on findability and reusability. Then followed a panel session about perspectives on F and R with Caspar Jordan (SND), Cecilia Björkdahl (KI), Jonas Fransson (MAU), Leif Longva (UiT), and Max Petzold (SND), chaired by Helena Rohdén,

At SND's network meeting in October, Leif Longva shared his experiences from the DAU work in The Arctic University of Norway (UiT).

Communications Officer at SND. After the panel, the participants were divided into smaller groups to discuss the practical aspects of working with the F and R in FAIR.

The day after the network meeting, there was a meeting for the archivists and other staff in the network who work with archival issues.

26–27 November, Bits and Pieces on Research Data

SND's final network meeting in 2019 took place in Lund. The programme for the two half-days targeted questions about the work with research data from various perspectives. During day one, representatives from Lund University discussed the process of creating a function for research data support. The participants were also given a brief overview of the training initiatives for doctoral students from five different faculty libraries, and a short introduction to population research by Domain Specialists Anna Axmon and Elisabeth Strandhagen. Maggie Hellström presented RDA and the activities in the Swedish RDA node.

Day two had parallel tracks, where the participants could choose between sessions on how network members can become certified as trusted data repositories, challenges for licenses on research data, how to host workshops on data management plans, and creating a guide for establishing a DAU.

During this network meeting there was also an informal meeting for the network's legal officers in order to discuss the need for a sub-network with a focus on legal questions. This meeting was chaired by Erica Schweder, SND's new Legal Officer.

Consortium DAU Council

During 2019, SND has appointed a group of consortium members that will function as a DAU Council. The purpose of this council is to strengthen the collaboration and communication between SND's steering committee, the consortium, and the national SND network. The new DAU Council has a representative from each of the members in the SND Consortium. Elisabeth Strandhagen, Deputy Director of SND and Collaboration Manager for the SND Network, is convenor and will lead the group's work.

Pilot Project with Local DAUs

During the year, SND ran a pilot project with some of the universities and research organisations in the SND network, in order to try out the new operative model for local data management. The purpose of the pilot project was to test a workflow where the local DAU

managed and published metadata and research data from one or more researchers. This process included creating routines for the work processes and trying out the tools and resources that SND have developed for the workflow. It was also a test of SND's new operative model, where the review, publishing, and storage of research data are local.

Eight network members participated in the pilot project. SND held workshops where representatives from each of the eight DAUs could test the workflow for publishing research data in the SND catalogue. Researchers also participated in some of these workshops. The role of SND Gothenburg has been to support and guide the DAU representatives, and, while doing so, establish new routines for communication between the DAUs and SND Gothenburg.

Members of the SND Network (2019)

Consortium members in bold text.

1. Blekinge Institute of Technology
2. **Chalmers University of Technology**
3. Dalarna University
4. Halmstad University
5. Jönköping University
6. Karlstad University
7. **Karolinska Institutet**
8. Kristianstad University Sweden (*New member*)
9. **KTH Royal Institute of Technology**
10. Linköping University
11. Linnaeus University
12. Luleå University of Technology
13. **Lund University**
14. Malmö University
15. Mid Sweden University
16. Mälardalen University
17. RISE Research Institutes of Sweden (*New member*)
18. Stockholm School of Economics
19. **Stockholm University**
20. Swedish Defence University
21. Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
22. **Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences**
23. Södertörn University
24. **Umeå University**
25. University College Stockholm (*New member*)
26. University of Borås
27. **University of Gothenburg**
28. University of Gävle
29. University of Skövde
30. University West
31. **Uppsala University**
32. Örebro University

Internal Projects

During 2019, SND staff were involved in a number of internal projects. These projects aimed to further the SND operations by developing new and existing tools and services for the benefit of the network members as well as for researchers. All of the internal projects are executed within the SND office, but build on support from SND's wider network, in various forms.

Adaptations of the Data Description Form

A new and improved version of the SND data description form was launched in 2019, with subject-specific metadata profiles and an updated layout. Adapting the metadata profile has been one of SND's largest web development projects in recent years. The general profile for describing research data in the form was

complemented by five specific profiles: archaeology and history, earth and environmental sciences, language resources, medical and health sciences, and social science. The resulting profiles were applied to the data description form, where researchers can describe, upload and publish their study descriptions in the SND research data catalogue. In addition, the form was given a cleaner look and a more user-friendly interface.

DORIS

In 2019, SND initiated a large-scale development project to build a comprehensive system where researchers can publish their research data and make them accessible. The objective is to create an online tool (Data Organisation and Information System, DORIS) that can be used throughout the entire research data management process; from data description and uploading of research data, to ordering data for reuse or review. This project is headed by an internal project group with the help of three reference groups: the SND data coordination forum, a group of DAU representatives, and a group of SND's domain specialists and other researchers.

The DAU Handbook

The DAU Handbook group has two main tasks: to create and, as needed, update data management specifications, and the DAU Handbook. The data management

The screenshot shows a web interface for the SND data description form. On the left, there are three buttons: 'Preview' (blue), 'Update status' (red), and 'Download as zip' (grey). Below these is a section for downloading metadata and files. A 'Legend' section explains that fields with a red square symbol are mandatory. The main form area has two radio buttons for 'Data are accessible by order' and 'Access to data is restricted'. Below that is a 'Research area' section with a dropdown menu. The dropdown is open, showing options: 'General' (selected), 'Earth and Environmental sciences', 'Language resources', 'Social science', 'Medical and Health Sciences', and 'Archaeology and History'. A 'Show more' link is visible below the dropdown.

In SND's data description form researchers can describe, upload, and publish their data. The general profile for describing research data in the form was complemented by five specific profiles in 2019. The form was also given a new, more user-friendly layout.

specifications outline the requirements for data and metadata that are to be made accessible in the SND research data catalogue. The handbook is a support resource in the Data Access Units' quality control process. These controls fulfil the requirements on quality in the specifications, and also partly fulfil the FAIR data principles. The group consists of members from the SND office and from various DAUs. Work on the DAU Handbook started in 2018, and it will be launched during 2020.

Data Management Resources

During 2019 SND staff created new, and updated existing, data management resources on our website. These resources are aimed at researchers and are meant to provide support throughout the research process, from planning to making data accessible and preparing them for re-use. The new data management resources will be published on the SND website during 2020.

Website and Graphic Profile

In 2018, SND adopted a new graphic profile to further visualize the major changes to the business model that came into place after forming a consortium. The changes in operations were also intended to be reflected on the SND website, and in 2019 an internal project group was appointed accordingly. The object of the Website Group is to restructure information and increase usability to provide better access to the resources on the website, as well as to implement the new graphic profile. At the end of 2019, SND's website had a new structure and look.

International Cooperation

SND is part of a global, interoperable and accessible infrastructure, where international cooperation plays a central role. During 2019, SND has continued its international cooperation, mainly by participating in the work within ESFRI landmarks in the Social & Cultural Innovation domain¹, such as the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)² and the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN)³.

CESSDA

The mission of CESSDA is to provide a full-scale sustainable research infrastructure that enables the research community in the social sciences to conduct high-quality research, which contributes to the production of effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today, and to facilitate teaching and learning.

CESSDA started in 1976 as an informal umbrella organisation for European national social science data archives. After being on the ESFRI Roadmap since 2006, it became a legal institution (CESSDA AS) in 2013 and then an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) in 2017.

At the end of 2019, the CESSDA consortium was composed of nineteen member countries and one observer. Each member country has a designated Service Provider (SP) that meets the specific demands and requirements of CESSDA. SND is the appointed Swedish SP.

The CESSDA Strategy builds on four pillars: trust, training, technology, and tools & services. For each of these pillars there are CESSDA Working Groups, and within these groups there are projects and meetings. The yearly CESSDA Work Plan includes a number of tasks to be carried out in partnership by the SPs. SND was involved in five tasks included in the Work Plan 2019⁴: *CESSDA Widening Activities; CESSDA Training Work Plan; Euro Question Bank; Technical Framework; CESSDA Trust Activities.*

CLARIN

CLARIN makes digital language resources available to scholars, researchers, students and citizen-scientists from all disciplines, especially in the humanities and social sciences, through single sign-on access. CLARIN is a distributed network consisting of the CLARIN ERIC, national consortia, centres of expertise of various types, and online services. CLARIN was established as an ERIC in 2012 and Sweden joined the CLARIN ERIC in 2014. Until and including 2019, SND was part of the Swe-Clarín consortium.

During 2019, SND's Swe-Clarín team has prepared for leaving the consortium. The CLARIN-adapted metadata profile and resource catalogue have been fully integrated with SND's general catalogue, and are included in the current development of a new system for data and metadata organisation (DORIS). The team has also provided support and assistance in the continued work

¹<http://roadmap2018.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/browse-the-catalogue/?domain=Social+%26+Cultural+Innovation>

²<https://www.cessda.eu/>

³<https://www.clarin.eu/>

⁴<https://www.cessda.eu/About/Projects/Work-Plans/Work-Plan-2019>

to re-design the Swe-Clarín website. Team members have further extended SND's expertise in data types related to CLARIN-associated resources, mainly focusing on various forms of text data.

Other International Cooperations

The Swedish membership in the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)⁵ is administered by SND. SND awards scholarships for participating in the ICPSR's Summer Program in Quantitative Methods of Social Research⁶, and in 2019 eight scholarships were awarded.

The participation in international organisations within the areas of metadata standards and persistent identifiers has continued through the memberships in the DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) Alliance⁷ and DataCite⁸. SND staff are also represented in the CoreTrustSeal⁹ Assembly of Reviewers. Other international memberships are the International Federation of Data Organisations (IFDO)¹⁰, and the World Data System (WDS)¹¹.

In June 2019, Sweden was one of six countries selected as new RDA (Research Data Alliance)¹² Europe nodes. The Swedish node¹³ is set up as a sub-unit of SND. To align with key national and European projects of relevance, RDA SE will investigate the research community in order to identify hot topics and needs, and map these to RDA groups. RDA SE will liaise with relevant stakeholders, policy makers, and professional bodies, to discuss high-priority RDM-related topics and how to address these from a national and Nordic perspective.

Through CESSDA, SND mentors the Macedonian data archive MK DASS. SND payed them a visit during CESSDA Widening in Skopje.

In the beginning of January 2019, SND applied to host the 46th annual conference for IASSIST (International Association for Social Science Information Services & Technology)¹⁴. Together with Göteborg & Co, SND wrote a thorough application, and on 22 January it was announced that the 2020 IASSIST conference¹⁵ will be arranged in Gothenburg with SND as host organisation. The conference will take place 19–22 May 2020 and the conference theme is *Data by Design: Building a Sustainable Data Culture*.

New Projects

SND participates in three infrastructure projects that started in 2019. These projects are funded by the European Commission under the H2020 Programme. SND also takes part in one Cost Action project.

ARIADNEplus¹⁶ is the extension of the previous ARIADNE project (2013–2017), which successfully integrated archaeological data infrastructures in Europe, indexing in its registry about 2 million datasets. The new project will build on the ARIADNE results, extending and support-

⁵<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/>

⁶<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/sumprog/>

⁷<http://www.ddialliance.org/>

⁸<https://datacite.org/>

⁹<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

¹⁰<http://ifdo.org/>

¹¹<https://www.icsu-wds.org/>

¹²<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

¹³<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-sweden>

¹⁴<https://iassistdata.org/>

¹⁵<https://iassist2020.org/>

¹⁶<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

ing the research community and further developing the relationships with key stakeholders. The ARIADNEplus data infrastructure will be embedded in a cloud that will offer the availability of Virtual Research Environments where data-based archaeological research may be carried out. The project will furthermore develop a Linked Data approach to data discovery, with innovative services, such as visualisation, annotation, text mining and geo-temporal data management.

SND is participating in 10 WPs as a content provider, technical partner, and a national coordinator. SND is also WP leader for Work Package 15 (Innovative Services for Users) and a Steering Committee member. The project started in January 2019 and runs for 48 months.

EOSC-Nordic¹⁷ is a project aiming to facilitate the coordination of initiatives relevant to EOSC¹⁸ (European Open Science Cloud) within the Nordic and Baltic countries. The project aims to exploit synergies to achieve greater harmonisation in policy and service provisioning across these countries, in compliance with EOSC-agreed standards and practices.

The project started in September 2019 and will end in August 2022. SND participates in two work packages: FAIR data (WP4), and Open Research data and services – demonstrators (WP5).

SSHOC¹⁹ (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) is a cluster project to create an open cloud ecosystem for the social sciences and humanities. The objective is to create a common European platform, where data, tools, and training resources are gathered in one place. With FAIR as a guiding principle, SSHOC will make it easier for researchers to share, find, and re-use high quality

data, and to find useful analysis tools. SSHOC is one of five EU funded cluster projects that will run from 2019 through to 2022. The project is a collaboration between 47 European organisations, coordinated by CESSDA. The results will be integrated in the larger platform EOSC, where European resources will be pooled and made accessible.

SND is participating in two tasks, Data and Metadata Interoperability Hub (T3.5) and Certification Plan for SSHOC Repositories (T8.2).

SEADDA²⁰ (Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age) is a Cost Action project that will bring together an interdisciplinary network of archaeologists and computer scientists. There is a will to make archaeological data open and freely accessible but the domain lacks appropriate, persistent repositories. Due to the fragility of digital data and the non-repeatable nature of most archaeological research, the domain is poised to lose a generation of research to the Digital Dark Age. To mitigate this, the project will create publications and materials that will set out a state-of-the-art standard for archaeological archiving across Europe, and recommendations that allow archaeologists and data management specialists to address problems in the most appropriate way.

The project started in April 2019 and runs until March 2023. SND participates as Steering group member/ Management committee member and as Vice Chair in Working Group 1: Stewardship of Archaeological Data. In November 2019, SND hosted a one-day SEADDA workshop centred on discussions on the situation for archaeological data and an outlining of a survey of the international state-of-the-art.

¹⁷<https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

¹⁸<https://www.eosc-portal.eu/>

¹⁹<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/>

²⁰<https://www.seadda.eu/>

Dissemination Statistics

At the end of 2019, SND had 2,009 searchable studies from a variety of research areas.

Downloaded Material

An increasing number of studies in the SND catalogue are freely accessible to download. Direct downloads from the SND website leapt from 4,032 in 2018 to 24,088 in 2019. The most downloaded dataset was *Inequality measures based on election data 1871 and 1892 for Swedish municipalities* (SND 1098-001) with 1,884 downloads.

Orders

Many studies that are not available to download can be ordered from the SND catalogue. In 2019 SND received 533 orders, resulting in the dissemination of 2,141 datasets.

Collections

Studies that form part of a collection or series are among the most popular orders. The two collections with by far the greatest number of orders in 2019 were the National Society Opinion Media (SOM) surveys and the Swedish National Election Studies. The Swedish part of the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)¹, the SVT Exit Poll Surveys and the Media Barometer were also popular in 2019.

Information for Students

In 2019, SND created a new webpage² aimed specifically at students. It provides tailored information and guidance to those seeking data appropriate for use as part of their studies.

YEAR	NUMBER OF ORDERS
2015	459
2016	521
2017	541
2018	523
2019	533

COLLECTIONS IN DEMAND	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
National SOM (Society Opinion Media)	308	478	537	406	473
Swedish National Election Studies – Parliamentary Elections	265	359	456	400	470
SVT Exit Poll Surveys	107	40	32	49	139
International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)*	95	94	117	131	97
Media Barometer	19	15	14	25	43
Swedish Electoral Data	28	20	32	29	37
Road Safety Survey	7	4	36	35	35
Western SOM	95	86	86	36	26
Swedish National Election Studies – European Parliament Elections	4	21	25	14	20
Total	928	1,117	1,335	1,125	1,340

¹ISSP changed access level during the year and is now available by direct download.

²<https://snd.gu.se/en/find-and-order-data/students>

TOP 10 DIRECT DOWNLOADS IN 2019

Inequality measures based on election data 1871 and 1892 for Swedish municipalities	1,884
Memorialisation in Norrtälje, Mariehamn and Pargas: 1881-1939	1,407
Oden Southern Ocean 2007/08 - Meteorological, Oceanographic and Ship Data Collected Onboard Icebreaker Oden - Nov 2007–Jan 2008	620
Reflection seismic study of the Siljan Ring impact structure: Mora - Migrated data	459
Medieval churches in Scania: Part A	380
Brexit Blog Corpus (BBC)	338
NordChild - The Nordic Study of Children's Health and Wellbeing	252
Swedish Contextual Database for The Swedish Generations and Gender Survey and The International Generations and Gender Programme	244
Noise exposure files for a polysomnographic study of ground-borne noise from railway tunnels and sleep - Pilot study	218
Observations of Noctilucent Clouds from Denmark during 2011	172
Total	5,974

DOWNLOADS AND DATASETS SUPPLIED

Downloads from the SND catalogue and datasets disseminated.

Downloads from Environment Climate Data Sweden (ECDS) were not included for 2017 or 2018 for technical reasons.

19th Century Inequality is Top of the 2019 Download Charts

There are a couple of different ways to access data that are listed in the SND data catalogue. Some datasets can be directly downloaded by clicking a button. Other datasets have to be ordered, and the order needs to be approved before the data can be accessed. Among the directly downloadable datasets, the top of the 2019 download statistics was the study “Inequality measures based on election data 1871 and 1892 for Swedish municipalities”. The creator of these data is economist Sara Moricz.

Sara Moricz holds a PhD in economics at Lund University and is currently working as a Data Analyst at IKEA Group. The data that she registered with SND were produced during her time as a doctoral student, when she, among other things, researched inequality in relation to income in Swedish municipalities during the 19th century.

– The data that I have given access to contain inequality measures that I have created, and the digitised raw data that I used to create these measures. The reason that I wanted to create inequality measures is that we still know very little about how inequalities in terms of income or wealth developed historically. Researchers in general are interested in these types of measures in order to view and analyse what inequality does for a society.

The data made available by Sara Moricz were the most downloaded in 2019.

Election Data Reveal Income Levels

It can be difficult to find information about income levels so far back in time, and it may require some detective work. In order to figure out what income people really had in the years 1871 and 1892, Sara Moricz used election data that reveal how many votes were used in municipal elections.

– In the late 19th century, Sweden had a tax-weighted electoral system. This means that it wasn't “one person, one vote”, but that each individual had a certain number of votes based on how much taxes they paid. The types of tax that determined which number of votes each voter had in municipal elections were agricultural property tax, other property taxes, and taxes on capital and labour income, which is what is normally taxed today.

The results from Sara Moricz' research reveal that the richest individuals in the industrial sector got more

money to spend between 1871 and 1892. This strengthens the image of an increase in financial inequality during the early industrialisation period in Sweden. Sara Moricz says that she has given a lot of thought to how you can use the data that she collected.

– The inequality measures can be used as ranking or index variables, which state whether Municipality A is more or less unequal than Municipality B. However, you can't tell exactly how unequal they are, as the source data are in many ways incomplete. I would say that the inequality measures are an end product that you might possibly build on, whereas you can use the raw data to do something else.

Would Like to See the Data Being Re-used

The decision to make the data from her research project accessible was easy for Sara Moricz. As far as possible, she would like to contribute to a higher standard for research and to pave the way for future research findings.

– I published the data so that people would be able to use them. And I was very surprised to hear that they were the most downloaded datasets. But if I can contribute to research and societal development by making data accessible, so that others can continue the work and do something with the data, I am only happy to do so.

Economy

Notes

1. Three new members joined the SND Network.
2. The number of CESSDA Tasks has diminished.
3. Internal co-financing of previous CESSDA Tasks.
- 4.-5. Unknown when estimating revenues. *Travel remuneration only.
- 6.-7. Lower staff and operating costs due to leave of absence.
8. Purchase of the domain name researchdata.se and new software.
9. Invited speakers at a workshop 2018.
10. Unknown when estimating university costs.
11. More assets than estimated were fully depreciated.
12. Please see note no 3.
13. Unspent funds within a project cooperation with another department.
14. Negative interest for university bank funds.
- 15.-16. Lower staff travel and conference costs due to leave of absence.
17. Higher participation rates at conferences and meetings organised by SND.
18. Lower costs for DoSp Coordinator and activities due to hiring late in the year.

The ending balance shows an accumulated capital of 6.98 million SEK, which will be used for activities within the SND Network over a three-year period.

Figures stated in thousand SEK

	Notes	Results	Budget
REVENUES			
Government grants		7,000	7,000
Swedish Research Council, Core activities		13,000	13,000
Swedish Research Council, CESSDA activities		1,000	1,000
Other income – SND Network Services	1.	1,725	1,500
Other income – CESSDA Tasks	2.	552	672
Internal co-financing SND	3.	48	0
EU project ARIADNEPlus		1,812	794
EU project SSHOC		795	461
EU project EOSC-Nordic	4.	300	0
EU project SEADDA	5.*	16	0
Swedish Research Council, ICPSR		350	350
Internal co-financing GU		121	0
Subsidised salaries		257	0
Other income		8	0
Accruals		-1,935	0
Total Revenues		25,047	24,777
EXPENSES			
<i>Fixed expenses</i>			
Staff	6.	-17,567	-17,873
Facilities		-1,084	-1,084
Other operating costs	7.	-691	-787
IT infrastructure		-201	-200
IT licenses	8.	-111	-80
Membership fees		-177	-175
Consulting fees	9.	-52	0
University IT fee incl. support		-459	-457
University overhead	10.	-2,100	-2,066
Depreciation	11.	-40	-144
Internal co-financing	12.	-48	0
SND scholarships for transfer		-134	-120
Return of unspent funds (Swe-Clarín)	13.	-358	0
University negative bank interest rates	14.	-91	0
Exchange loss		-6	0
<i>Total</i>		-23,120	-22,986
<i>Activity expenses</i>			
Staff travel	15.	-649	-980
Conference/course fees (staff training)	16.	-110	-234
SND conferences (SND org.)	17.	-487	-304
DoSp*/Consortium activities	18.	-405	-1,356
<i>Total</i>		-1,651	-2,874
Total Expenses		-24,770	-25,860
RESULT		277	-1,083
Opening balance 2019		6,702	
Ending balance 2019		6,979	

Staff

SND Gothenburg

Administration and Services

Director
Max Petzold

Administrator,
Language Coordinator
Lisa Isaksson

Communications
Officer
Matilda Lindmark

Communications
Officer
Helena Rohdén

Financial
Administrator
Ann Nordström

Legal Officer
Erica Schweder

Legal Officer
Kristina Ullgren

Senior Advisor
Iris Alfredsson

Senior Advisor
Birger Jerlehg

Without picture:

Financial Administrator, Sverker Jacobsson
Project Coordinator, Daniel Knezevic

Repository and Training

Deputy Director,
Team Leader
Elisabeth Strandhagen

Administrative
Coordinator
Eira Brandby

Data Manager
Jeremy Azzopardi

Data Manager
Martin Brandhagen

Data Manager
Dimitar Popovski

Data Manager
Sofia Österberg
(previously Agnesten)

Domain Specialist in
the Humanities
Stefan Ekman

Research Data
Advisor
Linda Härdelin

Research Data
Advisor
Ulf Jakobsson

Research Data
Advisor
Caspar Jordan

Research Data
Advisor
Ilze Lace

Research Data
Advisor
Sara Svensson

Researcher
David Rayner

Service
Coordinator
Rufus Latham

Without picture:
Malin Lundgren,
Data Manager

IT and Development

Head of IT
Johan Fihn Marberg

IT Architect
Pablo Millet

IT Architect
Olof Olsson

System Developer
Alireza Davoudian

System Developer
Stefan Jakobsson

System Developer
Tobias Linde

System Developer
Fabian Samuelsson

Without picture:
IT Technician, Akira Olsbänning
System Developer, Hasse Lans
System Developer, Joakim Larsson

Domain Specialists

Gustav Nilssonne
Coordinator
Karolinska Institutet

Anna Axmon
Lund University

Margaretha Hellström
Lund University

Darren Spruce
MAX IV,
Lund University

Brian Kuns
Stockholm University

Anders Moberg
Stockholm University

Ida Taberman
Swedish University of
Agricultural Sciences

Ylva Toljander
Swedish University of
Agricultural Sciences

Anders Brändström
Umeå University

Christel Häggström
Umeå University

Xavier de Luna
Umeå University

Karina Nilsson
Umeå University

Marcus Lundberg
Uppsala University

Without picture:

Fredrik Bolmsten, MAX IV, Lund University
Pontus Hennerdal, Stockholm University

As well as Iris Alfredsson, Stefan Ekman and Elisabeth Strandhagen, who act as Domain Specialists at University of Gothenburg.

Steering Committee

Swedish National Data Service is run by a consortium consisting of nine universities. The steering committee of SND is made up of representatives from each of these universities. Chalmers University of Technology and KTH Royal Institute of Technology joined the consortium late 2019, and had not yet appointed committee members at the end of the year.

Members

Göran Landberg (Chair)

Deputy Vice-Chancellor and Professor, Institute of Biomedicine,
University of Gothenburg

Mikael Hjerm

Professor, Department of Sociology, Umeå University

Lars Burman

Chief Librarian, Uppsala University

Karin Grönvall (substituted by Malin Jenslin)

Chief Librarian, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

Astri Muren

Deputy Vice-Chancellor and Professor, Department of Economics,
Stockholm University

Cecilia M. Björkdahl

Project Leader at Grants office, Karolinska Institutet

Monica Lassi

IT Architect at LUNARC, Centre for Scientific and Technical Computing,
Lund University

Swedish National Data Service

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